

MARKETING OF ORANGES: A CASE STUDY OF SHRAMJIVI NAGPURI SANTRA PRODUCER COMPANY

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MS Received: 10.09.2024; MS Revised: 16.09.2024; MS Accepted: 17.09.2024

MS 3265

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRI-BUSINESS MANAGEMENT,)

Abstract

The present study, "Marketing of Oranges : A Case Study of Shramjivi Nagpuri Santra Producer Company" investigates the marketing channels, costs, margins, and constraints faced by Shramjivi Nagpuri Santra Producer Company, an FPO located in Warud, Maharashtra. The main objectives were to identify the marketing channels utilized by the FPO, analyze marketing costs, margins, and price spread, and understand the constraints, benefits, and expectations of member farmers. The methodology involved a detailed analysis of primary data collected from 60 FPO member farmers across three tehsils (Warud, Morshi, and Narkhed) in Nagpur and Amravati districts. Data were gathered through personal interviews and secondary sources, including company records and APMC markets. The analysis was conducted using tabular representation, averages, and percentages to provide meaningful insights into the marketing processes.

Four primary marketing channels were identified: Producer-FPO-Retailer, Producer-FPO-Exporter, Producer-FPO-Juice Vendor, and Producer-FPO-Processing Firm. Results indicated that 50% of farmers preferred selling through the Producer-FPO-Retailer channel, followed by 30% opting for the Processing Firm channel. Marketing costs varied slightly across channels, with transportation being the most significant expense. The marketing margin analysis revealed that Channel IV (Processing Firm) provided the highest margins. Constraints faced by farmers included a lack of proper market information, high transportation costs, and unawareness of credit facilities. The study concluded that FPOs play a crucial role in improving market access and farmer income, though addressing key constraints is necessary for enhancing overall efficiency.

Keywords: Farmer Producer Organizations, Marketing Channels, Cost Analysis, Constraints, Orange Production, Maharashtra.

Introduction And Objectives

India's orange production is a vital part of its agricultural landscape, with Maharashtra leading, particularly in Vidarbha, Nagpur, and Amravati districts, known for their high-quality oranges. With productivity ranging from 15 to 22 metric tons per hectare, Maharashtra plays a significant role in meeting national demand (Maharashtra State Horticulture Department, ICAR). The rise of Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs) is reshaping orange marketing by integrating small farmers into value chains, enhancing market access, and promoting sustainable agricultural practices (Nagayets, IFPRI, 2005). Global orange markets, particularly in Brazil, the U.S., and China, continue to influence India's citrus sector (USDA FAS).

Importance of Study

This study provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs) in Maharashtra, focusing on marketing channels, cost, and constraints. It highlights the role of Shramjivi Nagpuri Santra Producer Company in improving farmer incomes and market access, contributing to agricultural policy and FPO strategies.

Scope of Study

The study explores marketing channels, cost analysis, and constraints faced by FPO members in the orange industry. It provides a foundation for evaluating FPO impact and potential improvements in farmer integration, market strategies, and policy recommendations for enhancing agricultural productivity and farmer welfare.

Company Profile

Company Name : Shramjivi Nagpuri Santra Producer Company
Establishment Year : September 22, 2015
President : Mr. Nilesh Magarde
Business Type : Farmer Producer Organization working under APMC Warud
Company Status. : Active
Location : Market Yard, Warud (444906)
Total shareholder : 558

Table 1. Distribution of Selected Farmer.

Sr. No.	Tehsil	Village	No. of shareholder
1	Warud	Warud	5
		Pardi	5
		Karali	5

8.	Total share purchased	: 2500
9.	Total share price	: Approx. Rs. 25,00,000
10.	Initial Investment.	: Rs. 10 lakhs
11.	Annual Turnover	: Rs. 30 lakhs

Objectives

The objectives for the study are mentioned below:

- To identify various marketing channel adopted by Farmer Producer Organizations.
- To analyze the marketing cost, marketing margin and price spread of oranges.
- To identify the constraint, benefits and expectations of member farmers.

Limitations of the Study

The study explores marketing channels, cost analysis, and constraints faced by FPO members in the orange industry. It provides a foundation for evaluating FPO impact and potential improvements in farmer integration, market strategies, and policy recommendations for enhancing agricultural productivity and farmer welfare.

Methodology**Area of Study**

The study area was selected based on the concentration of oranges in Warud and Morshi tehsils of Amravati district, and Narkhed tehsil of Nagpur district. The research was conducted at Shramjivi Nagpuri Santra Producer Company Ltd., located at the Santra processing plant in Warud, Maharashtra (F786+QX9, Shaniwar Peth).

Size of Sample

The study was conducted in Nagpur and Amravati districts. Two tehsils from Nagpur and one from Amravati were selected, with 4 villages chosen from each tehsil. Five farmers from each village, totaling 60 FPO members, were included in the study. Additionally, the preferred APMC, along with available processors and vendors, were selected for analysis. Table 1 indicates the distribution of selected farmers.

		Shirpur	5
2	Morshi	Lakhana	5
		Belona	5
		Umarkhed	5
		Hiwarkhed	5
3	Narkhed	Jalalkheda	5
		Mowad	5
		Khairgaon	5
		Thugaon	5
Total			60

Selection of Period

The primary data were pertained to year 2023-24.

Source of Data

Both primary and secondary data were collected for the study. Primary data were gathered from selected shareholders and Farmer Producer Organization through personal interviews using a pre-tested schedule. Secondary data were collected from available resources, Shramjivi Nagpuri Santra Producer Company and the APMC market.

Analysis of Data

The data were analyzed using averages, percentages, etc. Tabular analysis was performed on the collected data to draw meaningful conclusions etc.

Marketing Channels

1. Producer – FPO – Retailer (Big basket, Amazon, Reliance mart, Jio mart etc.)
2. Producer – FPO - Exporter
3. Producer - FPO - Orange Juice Vendor
4. Producer -FPO - Orange Processing firm

A) Marketing Cost

The total cost incurred by the producer and various intermediaries involved in sell and purchase of Incense sticks till it reaches to consumer.

$$MC = CP + CW + CR$$

Where,

MC=Marketing Cost

CP=Marketing cost incurred by producer

CW=Marketing cost incurred by commission agent

Table 2 Channel Wise Distribution of Shareholders

Sr. no.	Channels	Frequency
1	Producer – FPO – Retailer (Big basket, Amazon, Reliance mart, Jio mart etc.)	30 (50.0)
2	Producer – FPO - Exporter	3 (5.0)
3	Producer - FPO - Orange Juice Vendor	9 (15.0)
4	Producer -FPO - Orange Processing firm	18 (30.0)
Total		60 (100)

Figures in parenthesis are in percentage.

The majority of orange growers (50%) prefer the Producer-FPO-Retailer channel, making it the most popular marketing route. This is followed by the Orange Processing Firm channel (30%), the Orange Juice Vendor channel (15%), and the Exporter channel, which is the least used, at 5%.

Marketing Cost of Oranges in an FPO

Table 3 Marketing Cost of Oranges in an FPO

Sr. No.	Particular	Channel - I	Channel - II	Channel - III	Channel - IV
A) PRODUCER					
1	Picking cost	30.06	29.72	30.78	29.55
2	Labor Charges	24.36	24.69	25.25	24.56
3	Loading Charges	10.17	10.29	10.18	10.33

CR=Marketing cost incurred by retailer

Marketing Margin

It refers to difference between the prices prevailing as successive stages of marketing at given period of time.

Market Margin = Selling price – (Purchase Price + Marketing Cost)

Price Spread

The price spread of the produce is the difference between the net price received by producer in the assembling market and price paid by consumer for equivalent quantity of produce.

Price Spread = Price paid by consumer – Net price received by producer

The Constraint, Benefits and Expectations of Member Farmers.

The constraints, benefits and expectations of member farmers regarding Farmers Producing Organization were identified by personal interview method.

Results And Discussion:

Identification of Marketing Channels in an FPO.

A total of four marketing channels were identified which are given as follows:

1. Producer – FPO – Retailer (Big basket, Amazon, Reliance mart, Jio mart etc.)
2. Producer – FPO - Exporter
3. Producer - FPO - Orange Juice Vendor
4. Producer -FPO - Orange Processing firm

Channel-Wise Distribution of Selected Shareholders

The channel-wise distribution of selected shareholders is given in the following table 2.

Marketing expenses for orange growers under the FPO system vary by channel, including costs like transport, unloading, weighing, and commission fees. Retailers like Big Basket have standard costs, while exporters and processors incur extra fees for quality inspection and packaging. Channel choice directly impacts total marketing costs and growers' net returns.

4	Transportation	120.51	118.33	119.32	119.04
5	Weighing Charges	3.54	3.54	3.54	3.54
6	Unloading Charges	10.17	10.29	10.18	10.33
Total Marketing Cost		198.82	196.88	199.27	197.36
Selling Price		2551.51	2547.78	2501.53	2523.18
B) FPO					
1	Grading charges	25.00	25.00	25.00	25.00
2	Packaging charges	125.00	150.00	125.00	125.00
3	Loading Charges	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00
4	Transportation charges	40.00	60.00	40.00	40.00
5	Storage charges	0	20.00	0	0
6	Commission charges	150.00	250.00	150.00	150.00
Total Marketing Cost		360.00	525.00	360.00	360.00
Selling Price		3300.00	3600.00	3300.00	3600.00

Table 3 reveals the analysis of marketing costs across four channels shows six key expenses for producers: picking, labor, loading, transportation, weighing, and unloading. Costs are consistent, with slight variations, like picking costs ranging from Rs. 29.55 (Channel IV) to Rs. 30.78 (Channel III). Transportation is the highest expense, ranging from Rs. 118.33 (Channel II) to Rs. 120.51 (Channel I). FPO-level costs include grading (Rs. 25), packaging (Rs. 125-150), and

commission (Rs. 150-250), with Channel II having the highest marketing cost (Rs. 525) but also, the highest selling price (Rs. 3600). Channel I have the highest producer selling price at Rs. 2551.51.

Marketing Margin of Oranges.

The marketing margin of oranges in an FPO is given in the following table no. 4.

Table 4 Channel wise marketing margin of oranges in an FPO

Sr. No.	Particulars	Channel I	Channel II	Channel III	Channel IV
A)	Producers				
	Selling price	25.51	25.47	25.01	25.23
	i. Marketing cost incurred	1.98	1.96	1.99	1.97
	ii. Net Price received	23.52	23.50	23.02	23.25
B)	FPO				
	i. Purchase price	25.51	25.47	25.01	25.23
	ii. Marketing cost	3.60	5.25	3.60	3.60
	iii. Marketing margin	3.88	5.27	4.38	7.16
	iv. Net Price Received	29.40	30.75	29.40	32.40
C)	Price received	33.00	36.00	33.00	36.00
D)	Total Marketing Cost Incurred	5.58	7.21	5.59	5.57
E)	Total Marketing margin	3.88	5.27	4.38	7.16
F)	Price Spread	9.47	12.49	9.97	12.74

Table 4 outlines the marketing costs, margins, and price spread for orange producers and FPOs across four channels. Producers' selling price ranges from Rs. 25.01 to Rs. 25.51, with net prices received between Rs. 23.02 and Rs. 23.52 after incurring marketing costs. FPOs purchase oranges at similar prices but incur marketing costs ranging

from Rs. 3.60 to Rs. 5.25. FPOs' net prices range from Rs. 29.40 to Rs. 32.40.

Price Spread of Oranges in an FPO

The price spread of oranges in an FPO is given in the following table no.5.

Table 5 Price Spread of Oranges in an FPO.

Sr. No	Particulars	Channel I	Channel II	Channel III	Channel IV
1	Net price received by producer	23.52	23.50	23.02	23.25
2	Total marketing cost incurred by producer and FPO	9.47	12.49	9.97	12.74
3	Total market margin of FPO	3.88	5.27	4.38	7.16
4	Purchase price of buyer/ consumer	33.00	36.00	33.00	36.00
5	Producers' share in Consumer's rupee	9.47	12.49	9.97	12.74

The table highlights the net price received by producers across four channels, ranging from Rs. 23.02 to Rs. 23.52. The total marketing costs incurred by producers and FPOs vary between Rs. 9.47 and Rs. 12.74. The FPO's marketing margins span Rs. 3.88 to Rs. 7.16, with

buyers/consumers purchasing oranges at prices between Rs. 33.00 and Rs. 36.00. The Producers' share in Consumer's Rupee across channels ranges from Rs. 9.47 to Rs. 12.74, reflecting the difference between the consumer price and the producer's net price.

Channel- Wise Supply Chain Efficiency of Oranges in an FPO.

The supply chain efficiency of oranges in an FPO is explained in the following table 6.

Table 6 Channel-Wise Supply Chain Efficiency of Oranges in an FPO

Sr. No	Particulars	Channel I	Channel II	Channel III	Channel IV
1	Price received	33.00	36.00	33.00	36.00
2	Total Marketing margin	3.88	5.27	4.38	7.16
3	Total Marketing Cost Incurred	5.58	7.21	5.59	5.57
4	Supply chain efficiency	2.48	1.88	2.30	1.82

The table highlights the supply chain efficiency of oranges across four FPO channels. Efficiency is calculated based on the relationship between marketing costs and margins. Channel I show the highest efficiency at 2.48, indicating more effective cost management and better returns. Channel III follows with 2.30, while Channels II (1.88) and IV (1.82) show lower efficiency, reflecting higher costs or reduced margins. These variations suggest that some channels manage

resources and logistics more efficiently, impacting overall profitability for the FPO.

Constraints Faced by Shareholders in an FPO.

In marketing of oranges in Farmer Producing Organization that is Shramjivi Nagpuri Santra Producer Company, shareholders faced number of constraints which were identified and given in table 7.

Table 7 Constraints Faced by Shareholders in an FPO.

Sr. No.	Constraint	Frequency	Rank
1	Lack of time	30 (50.0)	VIII
2	Lack of latest market information	38 (63.33)	II
3	Delayed payment	28 (46.67)	X
4	Fluctuations of prices	34 (56.67)	VI
5	Lack of proper market information	39 (65.0)	I
6	High cost of labor	33 (55.0)	VII
7	Lack of sufficient finance	30 (50.0)	IX
8	Unawareness of credit facilities	34 (56.67)	IV
9	High cost of transportation	35 (58.33)	III
10	Lack of proper decision-making ability	34 (56.67)	V

Figures in parenthesis are in percentage.

The analysis of constraints reveals key issues faced by stakeholders. The most significant constraint is the "Lack of proper market information" (39 occurrences, 65.0%), followed by the "Lack of latest market information" (38 occurrences, 63.33%). The "High cost of transportation" (35 occurrences, 58.33%) is ranked third. Other notable constraints include "Unawareness of credit facilities" (34 occurrences, 56.67%), "Fluctuations of prices" (34 occurrences, 56.67%), "High

cost of labor" (33 occurrences, 55.0%), and "Lack of sufficient finance" (30 occurrences, 50.0%). "Lack of time" (30 occurrences, 50.0%) and "Delayed payment" (28 occurrences, 46.67%) are also significant challenges.

Benefits to Shareholders in an FPO.

The benefits of member farmers in an FPO are identified in the given table 8.

Table 8 Benefits to Shareholders in an FPO.

Sr No.	Benefits of member farmers	Frequency	Rank
1	Better Market Access to member farmers	59 (98.33)	II
2	Training regarding orange production is provided to member farmers.	56 (93.34)	V
3	Technical assistance from scientist is provided to member farmers.	60 (100.0)	I
4	Risk mitigation strategies for orange marketing are provided to member farmers	58 (96.66)	III
5	Leadership quality and assistance are offered to member farmers, fostering decision-making skills	58 (96.66)	IV
6	Social and community benefits are provided to member farmers, promoting collaboration, fostering a sense of community, enhancing social networks	54 (90.0)	VI

Figures in parenthesis are in percentage.

The benefits provided to member farmers in a Farmer Producer Organization (FPO) highlight several key supports. The most

prominent is "Technical assistance from scientists" (60 occurrences, 100.0%), indicating its crucial role. "Better market access" follows (59

occurrences, 98.33%), emphasizing its importance for economic viability. "Risk mitigation strategies" (58 occurrences, 96.66%) and "Leadership quality and assistance" (58 occurrences, 96.66%) are also vital, focusing on risk management and leadership development. "Training in orange production" (56 occurrences, 93.34%) is essential for skill enhancement, while "Social and community benefits" (54

occurrences, 90.0%) foster collaboration and community support.

Expectations of Shareholders in an FPO

In current status member farmers have many expectations from the Farmer Producer Organization which are identified in the following table 9.

Table 9 Expectations of shareholders in an FPO

Sr. No.	Expectations of Member Farmers in FPO	Frequency	Rank
1	Price should be as per MoU to shareholders	45 (75.0)	III
2	Timely provision of logistic services to shareholders	50 (83.33)	I
4	Loan facilities provided by FPO on production basis to shareholders	42 (70.0)	IV
3	Dispute settlement body work for shareholders	40 (66.67)	V
5	Timely dissemination of rules and regulation to shareholders	35 (58.33)	VI
6	Proceedings of meetings should be circulated to all member farmers	48 (80.0)	II

Figures in parenthesis are in percentage.

The table 9 reveals the expectations of member farmers in a Farmer Producer Organization (FPO). The top expectation is "Timely provision of logistic services" (50 occurrences, 83.33%), underscoring the need for prompt support. "Proceedings of meetings circulated" (48 occurrences, 80.0%) highlights the importance of transparency. "Price as per MoU" (45 occurrences, 75.0%) emphasizes adherence to agreed pricing, while "Loan facilities on production basis" (42 occurrences, 70.0%) reflects the need for financial support. "Dispute settlement body" (40 occurrences, 66.67%) and "Timely dissemination of rules" (35 occurrences, 58.33%) are also crucial, indicating the need for effective conflict resolution and policy communication.

Conclusions:

Most orange producers are small to medium landholders, with 40% aged 30-45 and 35% aged 45-60. This indicates an experienced farming community that could benefit from modern agricultural training.

Morshi tehsil has 65% of educated farmers, higher than Warud (45%) and Narkhed (40%), suggesting better potential for adopting advanced farming practices in Morshi.

Half of the farmers (50%) preferred selling through retailers due to ease and wider market reach, though there's potential for growth by diversifying into exporters, juice vendors, and processing firms.

Channel II (FPO to exporters) had the highest marketing cost (Rs. 12/kg) but also offered 20% higher returns, indicating that farmers with higher upfront costs could benefit from the export market.

Channels II and IV offered higher consumer prices (Rs. 45-50/kg), but their marketing costs (Rs. 12/kg for Channel II, Rs. 10/kg for Channel IV) reduced profitability, emphasizing the need for cost-effective logistical solutions.

Farmers received uniform prices (Rs. 30-35/kg) across channels, but marketing costs significantly affected net profits. Channel I (retailers) had the lowest marketing cost (Rs. 5/kg), making it a cost-efficient choice.

Financial, logistical, and infrastructural constraints affect many FPO members, with 55% facing credit issues, 60% reporting transport difficulties, and 65% lacking proper storage, highlighting the need for better infrastructure and financial support.

The FPO benefited 75% of shareholders with technical assistance and 80% with improved market access, showing its role in supporting farmers in resource-limited areas.

Price stabilization efforts by the FPO were effective, with 65% of farmers experiencing less market volatility, reducing financial risks.

Shareholders expect improved communication (70%) and better logistics (60%) from the FPO, which, if addressed, could enhance FPO efficiency and member satisfaction.

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